

Management

A STUDY ON PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT OF EMPLOYEES IN SHALOM GARMENTS, VALLIOOR

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Abstract

Performance management is an important driver in most companies today. Companies regard this as a tool to ensure the people working for them and deliver as per the agreed contract and objectives were set mutually. This study reveals the importance of a well-managed performance management system. The purpose of this research project is to find out the performance management of shalom garments, factors influencing performance of employees, relationship between performance and rewards. This research covers reward system, motivational factors, factors influencing performance of employees of shalom garments. The main findings are that, motivational talks of management towards employees are low, company does not provide opportunity to the employee's self-development and management does not take any steps to improve the literacy level of the employees.

Keywords: Performance; Employees Expectation; Satisfaction & Motivational Factors.

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1. Introduction

Performance is a product of ability and motivation of an individual measured through output produced in the form of tangible units or behavior exhibited by him/her. Performance Management is a strategic and integrated approach for delivering sustained success to organizations by improving the performance of the people by developing the capabilities of teams and individuals. Performance management – A management process for ensuring employees are focusing their work efforts in ways that contribute to achieve the agency's mission. It consists of three phases: (a) setting expectations for employee performance, (b)

maintaining a dialogue between supervisor and employee to keep performance on track, and (c) measuring actual performance relative to performance expectations.

2. Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out the factors that influence the performance of employees
- 2) To find out the satisfaction level of employees towards the performance management of the shalom garments

3. Methodology

Primary data forms a basis of the study. The researcher has selected Shalom Garments, Vallioor to study the performance management of the employees. 250 respondents were selected as sample size. The researcher has used simple random sampling method under probability method for obtaining information. Questionnaire was used to collect primary data from respondents. The secondary data regarding this study is collected from books, magazines, journals, relevant projects and internet. Weighted average technique is used to analyse and interpret the collected data.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The purpose of this study is to measure the performance as well as the satisfaction level of the employees.

Factors influencing the performance of employees

Weighted average method is used by the researcher to find out the factors which influence the performance of the employees. The results are given in the table 1

Table 1: Factors influencing the performance of employees

Factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Weighted Average
Reasonable periodical increase in salary	20	8	10	6	6	3.6
Skill and ability	14	20	4	8	4	3.64
Feedback	22	16	8	2	2	4.08
Incentives	34	8	6	2	0	4.44
Coaching	20	14	8	4	4	3.56
Organizational rules	16	14	10	4	6	3.6
Good relationship with co-workers	18	18	8	2	4	3.88
Motivational talks	12	18	12	6	2	3.64
Goal of the organization	20	26	0	14	0	4.64

Effective performance appraisal system	20	20	2	0	8	3.88
Leadership style	20	16	8	2	4	3.92
Attitude	16	6	14	6	6	3.28

Source: Primary data

(5=Strongly Agree, 4=Agree, 3=Neutral, 2=Disagree, 1=Strongly Disagree)

From the above table it was found that goal of the organization (4.64) only highly influences the employees, whereas the least rank is given to the attitude (3.28). The first rank is given to the goal of the organization, because goal only induce them to perform the expected task.

Satisfaction level of the employees towards Performance management

The satisfaction level of the employees is explained with the help of weighted average technique. It is explained below.

Table 2: Satisfaction level of employees towards Performance management

Factors	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Dis Agree	Strongly disagree	Weighted average
Performance management is helpful for improving the personnel skill	34	8	4	2	0	4.36
Satisfied with existing Performance Management system	30	6	2	10	2	4.04
Performance management is the base for effective training program	30	12	6	0	0	4.32
Performance management helps to identify the strength and weakness of the employees	24	16	8	2	0	4.24
Management fixes the salary based on the performance	28	8	2	6	4	3.88
Performance management clearly defines the job and responsibilities	28	10	2	8	2	4.08
Performance management encourages two way communication	24	10	4	6	4	3.76
The employees who are hardworking and results oriented are praised & rewarded in the org.	30	6	8	2	4	4.12
Performance mgt. communicate the company's objectives to employees	20	16	6	6	2	3.92
Performance management increase the feel of security in the minds of employees.	22	6	6	12	4	3.6

Source: Primary data

The above table inferred that the first rank is given “To improve the personnel skill (4.36)”, the second rank is given to “Effective training program(4.32)”, and the least rank is given to “Job security” (3.6). The first rank is given to the personnel skill, because the performance management helps to improve the skill by way of giving training to them.

4. Suggestions

- The company can allow the employees to attend refreshment courses to improve their knowledge.
- The rewards like coupons redeemable at stores, festival gifts, gain sharing also motivate the employees.
- The company can provide opportunity to employee’s self-development to improve their ability.
- The company should provide proper job security to the employees.

5. Conclusion

The researcher found that the goal of the organization induce the employees to perform the expected task and also it helps to improve the skill by way of giving training to them. So the performance management of the Shalom Garments helps to improve the performance of the employees working in that organization. It is based on the principles of measurement, appraisal, action and monitoring. However, it can be manifest in very different forms depending on whether the aim is to further improve good performers, or deal with underperformance. Performance Management can also apply to individuals, teams, groups or organizations.

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